

Synthesis, X-ray structure and molecular properties of a new cobalt(III) complex of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{SCN})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ [L = *N,N'*-(bis(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,2-ethanediamine]

Habibar Chowdhury*^a and Indrani Paul^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Kabi Nazrul College, Murarai, Birbhum-731 219, West Bengal, India

E-mail : habibar_hs@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, MUC Women's College, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

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Abstract : One new hexacoordinated cobalt(III)isothiocyanato complex of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{SCN})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ (**1**) [L = *N,N'*-(bis(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,2-ethanediamine] is isolated using a 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio of $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, L and NH_4NCS in a methanolic solvent at room temperature. The compound **1** has been characterized using microanalytical, spectroscopic, X-ray crystallographic and other physicochemical results. Structure of $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{SCN})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ (**1**) is solved by X-ray diffraction measurements. **1** crystallizes in the monoclinic space group C2/c. Some crystal data are : $a = 12.3151(3)$ Å, $b = 12.7842(3)$ Å, $c = 18.7199(5)$ Å, $\beta = 99.365(2)^\circ$ and $Z = 4$. Cobalt(III) center in **1** has a distorted octahedral coordination environment with a CoN_4S_2 chromophore ligated by four N atoms of the tetradentate Schiff base and two S atoms of S-coordinated SCN^- ions mutually in *trans* orientation. The mononuclear units in **1** are engaged in weak cooperative intermolecular C-H \cdots N and C-H \cdots O hydrogen bonds and $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions resulting cage-like 3D network structure. Room temperature solid-phase magnetic susceptibility measurement show that complex **1** is diamagnetic (t_{2g}^6 , $S = 0$). In CV, a quasi-reversible one-electron reductive response due to cobalt(III)-cobalt(II) couple is observed in **1**. Compound **1** displays intraligand $^1(\pi\text{-}\pi^*)$ fluorescence and intraligand $^3(\pi\text{-}\pi^*)$ phosphorescence in glassy solutions.

Keywords : Cobalt(III)isothiocyanate, Schiff base, superstructure, redox behaviour, thermal behaviour, luminescence property.

Introduction

Research on design and synthesis^{1,2} of mono-, di- and polynuclear coordination compounds of cobalt in its different oxidation states has spawned great interest due to their exciting synthetic, structural, spectroscopic and magnetic features³⁻⁶. One-pot reaction⁷ of metal-ions, organic ligands and inorganic/organic terminals/bridges in pre-assigned molar ratios is one of the popular synthetic approaches to afford compounds with tunable properties. Schiff bases⁸ are useful organic ligands because of their preparative accessibilities, structural varieties and varied denticities. Thiocyanate⁹⁻¹¹, a heterotriatomic molecular ion rod, is now being used to isolate different functional coordination compounds due to their versatile terminal/bridging motifs. Cobalt is well suited¹ to this study since it permits a wide range of symmetries and

coordination numbers in its different oxidation states. Different research groups are interested¹²⁻¹⁴ in this field particularly with pseudohalides and organic blockers such as multidentate *N*-donor Schiff bases for the isolation of stable metal-organic frameworks (MOFs)¹⁵. This work stems from our interest to investigate the coordination behaviour of a tetradentate Schiff base, *N,N'*-(bis(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,2-ethanediamine (L, Scheme 1) towards cobalt(III) in combination with isothiocyanate. Successfully a new hexacoordinated cobalt(III)-isothiocyanato complex of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{SCN})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ (**1**) is isolated using a single-pot reaction of a 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio of $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, L and NH_4NCS in an alcoholic solvent at room temperature. Structure of **1** is solved using X-ray structural measurement. The details of synthesis, molecular and crystalline architectures, and

properties of **1** are described below.

Scheme 1. Framework of L with (NP, Nⁱ, NP, Nⁱ) donor set.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

Mononuclear [Co(L)(SCN)₂]ClO₄ (**1**) was obtained by the reaction of a 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio of Co(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O, L and NH₄NCS in a methanolic solvent at room temperature. X-Ray structural analysis confirms this composition. The reaction is reproducible, as is evident from repetitive microanalytical, spectral and electrochemical results. The reproducibility reflects an inherent tendency towards formation of the complex **1**. The reaction is summarized in eq. (1) :

The new complex was characterized by microanalytical (C, H and N), spectroscopic, thermal and other physicochemical results. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with the formulation **1**. The moisture-insensitive complex **1** is stable over long periods of time in powdery and crystalline states. It is soluble in organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. In MeCN solution compound **1** behaves a 1 : 1 electrolyte, as reflected from its conductivity value (120 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹)¹⁶. Room temperature solid-phase magnetic susceptibility measurement show that complex **1** is diamagnetic (t_{2g}^6 , $S = 0$).

Spectroscopic studies :

Infrared spectrum of **1** was recorded in KBr discs in the 4400–400 cm⁻¹ range. In **1**, the ν(C=N) + (C=C) stretching frequencies of the metal bound Schiff base are

observed at 1624 and 1592 cm⁻¹. ν(C=N) stretching vibration of the thiocyanate appears as a single and strong stretch at 2076 cm⁻¹; the nature and position of signal strongly suggest S-coordination of the isothiocyanate¹⁷. ν(C-S) stretching frequency is noticed at 778 cm⁻¹. Presence of ionic perchlorate bands is seen at 1090 and 620 cm⁻¹ as usual. Orange-red solution of **1** in MeCN shows two main bands observed at 550 nm and 360 nm which are characteristic of octahedral cobalt(III) environment involving ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transitions¹⁸. The band at 266 nm may be assigned to a ligand-based charge transfer transition¹⁹.

Crystal structure of [Co(L)(SCN)₂]ClO₄ (**1**) :

Single crystal X-ray structure determination of compound **1** was done to define the molecular structure and crystalline architecture. Structure analysis reveals that crystal lattice of **1** consists of mononuclear [Co(L)(NCS)₂]ClO₄ unit. Cooperative intermolecular C-H⋯N and C-H⋯O hydrogen bonds and π⋯π interactions in **1** result in a cage-like 3D network structure. An ORTEP diagram with atom labeling schemes and perspective views of the supramolecular structures are shown in Figs. 1-3. Selected bond distances and angles relevant to the coordination sphere are listed in Table 1. The relevant hydrogen bonds and π⋯π interaction parameters are set in Tables 2 and 3. The coordination polyhedron around cobalt(III) is best described as a distorted octahedron with a CoN₄S₂ chromophore (Fig. 1) ligated by four N atoms (N1, N2, N1_b, N2_b) of the tetradentate Schiff base (L) and two S atoms (S1, S1_b) of S-coordi-

Fig. 1. The fundamental coordination unit in **1** with atom numbering schemes.

nated SCN⁻ ions mutually in *trans* orientation. The coordination includes one chelated tetradentate ligand coordinated by two N^P (N1, N1_b) atoms and two N^I (N2, N2_b) atoms along with two terminal S^t (S1, S1_b) atoms of the two isothiocyanate (SCN) mutually in *trans* orientation. Two pyridine N^P atoms (N1, N1_b) and two imine N^I atoms (N2, N2_b) of **L** occupy the equatorial sites, whereas two terminal isothiocyanate S^t atoms (S1, S1_b) are in axial positions with bond angle 175.02(3)°. Distortion from the ideal octahedral geometry is due to asymmetric nature of **L** and the deviation of the refined angles (90°/180°) at the metal center. The organic blocker is folded in ethylenic part. Torsion angle of N2-C14-C14_b-N2_b is -30.4(3)°. It is of note that the distortion from ideal octahedral coordination is very significant from the ranges of *cisoid* [81.86(8)°–110.42(8)°] and *transoid* [167.07(9)°–175.02(3)°] angles, which show sufficient deviation from the ideal values (90°/180°). The sum (360.36°) of the equatorial angles [N1-Co1-N2 81.86(8)°, N1-Co1-N1_b 110.42(8)°, N2-Co1-N1_b 81.86(8)° and N2-Co1-N2_b 86.22(8)°] is close to 360°. This reflects that the equatorial N atoms and metal center are almost in a same plane. Two terminal isothiocyanate is coordinated in a linear fashion as seen from its S1-C1-N3 angle [179.0(4)°] and mutually in *trans* alignment with Co-N-C bond angles close to 90° [Co1-S1-C1 103.77(13)°] (Table 1). The two Co-N^I distances [Co1-N1 and Co1-N1_b 1.969(2) Å] are greater than two Co-N^P distances

[Co1-N2 and Co1-N2_b 1.8660(19) Å] reflecting the stronger coordination of N^P over N^I. The two Co-S^t distances are identical [Co1-S1 and Co1-S1_b 2.3048(7) Å]. In the terminal isothiocyanate ligand, the S1-C1 distance [1.664(4) Å] is smaller than C1-N3 distance [1.140(5) Å] which strongly reflects sulphur (S1) atom of SCN⁻ is coordinated to cobalt(III) center¹¹.

In the crystal packing, **1** adopts a 2D supramolecular sheet architecture through cooperative intermolecular C-H⋯N and C-H⋯O hydrogen bonds. The N atom (N3) of terminal isothiocyanate and *para*-hydrogen atom (H4) of pyridine ring of the Schiff base are engaged in weak intermolecular C-H⋯N [H4⋯N3, 2.5000 Å; C4⋯N3, 3.273(5) Å; C4-H4⋯N3, 140.00°] hydrogen bond (Table 2) and the one O atom (O2) of ionic perchlorate (ClO₄⁻) results in doubly intermolecular C-H⋯O [H6⋯O2, 2.3700 Å; C6⋯O2, 3.182(4) Å; C6-H6⋯O2, 146.00° and H9⋯O2, 2.1500 Å; C9⋯O2, 3.022(4) Å; C9-H9⋯O2, 155.00°] hydrogen bonds with two H atoms viz. *ortho*-hydrogen atom (H6) of pyridine ring and *ortho*-hydrogen atom (H9) of benzene ring of the Schiff base, resulting in a 2D (4,4) sheet structure (Fig. 2) along *ac*-plane. These 2D sheets in turn are further engaged in π⋯π interactions (Table 3) between pyridine rings Cg(4)-Cg(4) [Cg4-Cg4, 5.6506(17) Å, dihedral angles 52.19°; perpendicular distances between the baricenters 3.4641(12) Å] and benzene rings Cg(5)-Cg(5) [Cg5-Cg5, 5.1257(17) Å, dihe-

Fig. 2. Hydrogen bonded 2D sheet structure in **1** formed by C-H⋯O and C-H⋯N interactions along *ac*-plane.

Fig. 3. Cage-like 3D network structure in **1** formed by cooperative C-H...O and C-H...N hydrogen bonds and $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions.

dral angles 54.38° ; perpendicular distances between the baricentres $2.9852(11)$ Å] of different molecular units resulting in a cage-like 3D network structure (Fig. 3).

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles ($^\circ$) for **1**

Bond distances			
Co1-N1	1.969(2)	C11-O1	1.327(5)
Co1-N2	1.8660(19)	C11-O2	1.570(4)
Co1-N1_b	1.969(2)	C11-O1_a	1.327(5)
Co1-N2_b	1.8660(19)	C11-O2_a	1.570(4)
Co1-S1	2.3048(7)	S1-C1	1.664(4)
Co1-S1_b	2.3048(7)	C1-N3	1.140(5)
Bond angles			
N1-Co1-N2	81.86(8)	N1_b-Co1-N2_b	81.86(8)
N1-Co1-N2_b	167.07(9)	N1_b-Co1-S1	83.07(7)
N1-Co1-N1_b	110.42(8)	N1_b-Co1-S1_b	94.04(7)
N1-Co1-S1	94.07(7)	N2_b-Co1-S1	91.38(6)
N1-Co1-S1_b	83.07(7)	N2_b-Co1-S1_b	92.26(6)
N2-Co1-N2_b	86.22(8)	S1-Co1-S1_b	175.02(3)
N2-Co1-N1_b	167.07(9)	N3-C1-S1	179.0(4)
N2-Co1-S1	92.26(6)	Co1-S1-C1	103.77(13)
N2-Co1-S1_b	91.38(6)		

Symmetry code : ^(a)-x, y, 1/2-z; ^(b)1-x, y, 1/2-z

Redox behaviour :

The electroactivity of the complex **1** was examined in MeCN solution (0.1 M in TEAP) using cyclic voltammetry (CV) at a platinum working electrode. The complex shows nearly reversible ($\Delta E_p = 70$ mV) one-electron reductive response corresponding to cobalt(III)-cobalt(II) couple as is shown in eq. (2) :

The response is reproducible with no trace of decomposition after a number of cycles.

A representative voltammogram of **1** is shown in Fig. 4. The formal potentials lie close to 0.33 V vs SCE. One-electron nature of the couple was verified with comparison of standard sample²⁰.

Thermal behaviour :

Thermogravimetric (TG) analysis was carried out to examine thermal stability of the compound. The sample made from crushed single crystals was heated between 40 and 800 $^\circ\text{C}$ in the static atmosphere of dinitrogen at a heating rate of 10 $^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The TG curve (Fig. 5) shows that **1** is stable up to 194 $^\circ\text{C}$. The compound loses one L

Table 2. Hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1**

D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A	Symmetry code
C6-H6...O2 ^c	0.9300	2.3700	3.182(4)	146.00	^(c) 1/2+x, 1/2+y, z
C9-H9...O2 ^d	0.9300	2.1500	3.022(4)	155.00	^(d) 1-x, y, 1/2-z
C4-H4...N3 ^e	0.9300	2.5000	3.273(5)	140.00	^(e) 3/2-x, 1/2-y, 1-z

Table 3. $\pi \cdots \pi$ Interaction parameters (Å, °) for **1**

Cg-Cg	Cg-Cg distance	Dihedral angle (i, j)	Perpendicular distances between baricenters (i, j)	Slippage
Cg(4)-Cg(4) ^f	5.6506(17)	52.19	3.4641(12)	4.464
Cg(5)-Cg(5) ^g	5.1251(17)	54.38	2.9852(11)	4.166

Symmetry code : ^(f)3/2-x, 1/2-y, 1-z; ^(g)2-x, -y, 1-z; Cg(4) = N(1)→C(2)→C(3)→C(4)→C(5)→C(6); Cg(5) = C(8)→C(9)→C(10)→C(11)→C(12)→C(13).

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of **1** in MeCN at 298 K.

(obs. : 54.7%; calcd. : 55.23%) in the first step of its decomposition. The second step weight loss (obs. : 28.14%; calcd. : 33.74%) is in line with the removal of two thiocyanate. The final residue may be due to one CoO unit (obs. : 14.77%; calcd. : 13.85%).

Luminescence behaviour :

The photoluminescence behaviour of compound **1** was examined. **1** shows emission at 470 nm at 298 K. This is assignable to intraligand $^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ fluorescence. A repre-

Fig. 5. Thermal behaviour of **1**.

sentative pattern is shown in Fig. 6. The lifetime for **1** is 2.33 ns. In glassy solutions (77 K) a red shift is observable (550 nm for **1**) which is presumably due to $^3(\pi-\pi^*)$ phosphorescence^{21,22}.

Fig. 6. Fluorescence (—) at 298 K and phosphorescence (---) at 77 K of **1**.

Conclusion

In summary, one new hexacoordinated cobalt(III)-isothiocyanato compound containing a tetradentate Schiff base (**L**) as organic chelator has been isolated. X-Ray structural study shows that the molecular architecture of **1** consists of a CoN_4S_2 chromophore ligated by four N atoms of the tetradentate Schiff base and two S atoms of S-coordinated two terminal isothiocyanates ions mutually in *trans* orientation to cobalt(III) center in an octahedral coordination environment. The innocent zero-dimensional (0D) mononuclear units in **1** function as supramolecular synthons promoting dimensionality to 3D via cooperative intermolecular C-H \cdots N and C-H \cdots O hydrogen bonds and $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions. The compound is thermally stable, redox active and a good example of luminous material. This work on such compound illustrates a potentially versatile approach towards isolation of metal-organic framework.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), ethylenediamine (Spectrochem, India), ammonium thiocyanate (E. Merck, India), cobalt(II) carbonate (E. Merck, India) and perchloric acid (E. Merck, India) were pur-

chased from respective concerns and were used as received. Cobalt(II) perchlorate hexahydrate was prepared on treatment of cobalt(II) carbonate with perchloric acid followed by slow evaporation on steam-bath, filtration through a fine glass-frit, and preservation in a desiccator containing concentrated sulfuric acid (E. Merck, India) for subsequent use. The Schiff base, *N,N'*-(bis(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,2-ethanediamine (**L**) was prepared following a reported²³ procedure with a little modification. All other chemicals and solvents were AR grade and were used as received. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Caution! Perchlorate compounds of metal ions are potentially explosive²⁴ especially in presence of organic ligands. Only a small amount of materials should be prepared and handled with care.

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01(M) KCl solution, and MeCN was used as solvent. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility of powdered sample was measured on a CAHN electrobalance 7550 with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as a reference and diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants²⁵. Thermal behaviors were examined with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer heated from 40–800 °C under nitrogen. Ground state absorptions measurements (in MeCN) were made with a Shimadzu model UV-2450 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Solid state fluorescence measurements were done using a Perkin-Elmer LS55 fluorescence spectrometer.

Synthesis of $[\text{Co}(\text{L})_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ (**1**) :

To a $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.365 g, 1 mmol) solution in MeOH (10 mL), **L** (0.418 g, 1 mmol) dissolved each in the same solvent (10 mL) was added dropwise. To this solution mixture, a solution of NH_4NCS (0.076 g, 1 mmol) in the same solvent (10 mL) was added. The final deep red solution was left undisturbed in an open air for slow evaporation. The microcrystal of **1** that deposited after a week was collected by filtration and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 0.404 g (75%). Anal. Calcd. for

C₂₈H₂₂N₆O₄ClS₂Co (**1**) : C, 50.6; H, 3.3; N, 12.6. Found : C, 50.8; H, 3.1; N, 12.3%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν(C=N) + (C=C) 1624, 1592; ν(C=N) 2076; ν(ClO₄) 1090, 620; UV-Vis (MeCN), λ_{max}/nm (10⁻³ ε M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) : 550, 360, 266; Λ_M (MeCN, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 120; E^o₂₉₈, V (ΔE_p, mV) for Co^{III/II} : 0.33 (70).

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

Single crystal of **1** suitable for X-ray analyses was selected from those obtained by open evaporation of MeOH solution of the reaction mixtures at 298 K. Crystallo-

graphic data were collected on a Bruker KAPPA APEX II CCD diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo-Kα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å) at 296(2) K. The detector frames were integrated by the use of the program SAINT²⁶ and absorption corrections were performed with SADABS²⁷. Of the 14681 total reflections for the complex **1**, 3724, with [I > 2σ(I)] were used for structures solutions. The structure was solved by direct methods using SHELXTL²⁸. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters whereas hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions where possible and given isotropic U values 1.2 times that of the atom to which they are bonded. Materials for publication were prepared using SHELXL-2013²⁹, SHELXTL, PLATON³⁰, Mercury 3.3³¹ and ORTEP-32³² programs. A summary of the crystallographic data and structure determination parameters of this complex is given in Table 4.

Table 4. Crystallographic data and structure refinement parameters for **1**

Crystallographic parameters	1
CCDC Number	1494008
Chemical formula	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ ClS ₂ Co
Formula mass	665.04
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C2/c (No. 15)
a (Å)	12.3151(3)
b (Å)	12.7842(3)
c (Å)	18.7199(5)
α (°)	90.00
β (°)	99.365(2)
γ (°)	90.00
V (Å ³)	2907.96(13)
T (K)	296
λ (Å)	0.71073
Z	4
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.871
ρ _{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.519
F(000)	1360
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.22×0.24×0.26
θ ranges (°)	2.2 to 28.7
h/k/l	-16,16/-17,16/-25,25
Reflections collected	14681
Independent reflections	3724
T _{max} and T _{min}	0.9325 and 0.7296
Data/restraints/parameters	3724/0/196
R _{int}	0.026
Final R ₁ values (I > 2σ(I))	0.0453
Final wR(F ²) values (I > 2σ(I))	0.1701
Goodness of fit on F ²	1.16
Largest peak and hole (e Å ⁻³)	0.55 and -0.75
Weighting scheme : R = Σ F ₀ - F _c /Σ F ₀ , wR = [Σw(F ₀ ² - F _c ²) ² /Σw(F ₀ ²) ²] ^{1/2} , Calcd. w = 1/[σ ² (F ₀ ²) + (0.1000P) ² + 0.0000P], where P = (F ₀ ² + 2F _c ²)/3	

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, No. 1494008 (**1**). Copy of this information can be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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